

Kinetics of Oxidation of Formic Acid by Chromium Peroxydichromate^(a)

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The kinetics of oxidation of formic acid by chromium peroxydichromate in aqueous medium has been reported. A first order dependence in peroxydichromate and second order in formic acid has been observed. Negative salt effect (KCl and K_2SO_4) and positive solvent effect (acetic acid) have been found. A plausible mechanism consistent with the experimental results has been proposed. Various Arrhenius parameters have been calculated.

CHROMIUM peroxydichromate has recently been used in the oxidation of many organic compounds¹⁻⁵. The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of formic acid by chromium peroxydichromate in an aqueous medium has been investigated and the findings are presented here.

Experimental

Chromium peroxydichromate was prepared by the method described earlier⁶. Stock solution of an appropriate concentration of formic acid (E. Merck) was prepared. The other chemicals used were of B.D.H. AnalaR grade.

Kinetics of the reaction was followed by iodometric estimation of Cr(VI) in aliquot portions of the reaction-mixture at different intervals.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic studies were performed by taking formic acid in sufficient excess over the oxidant concentration. The rate of oxidation observed first order kinetics uniformly with oxidant concentration (Fig. 1). The pseudo first order rate constants (k_1) were evaluated from the integrated form of first order rate equation at different initial concentrations of formic acid and peroxydichromate (Table 1).

Results of Table 1 show that there is a small change in pseudo first order rate constant (k_1) for different sets of experiments, indicating that the rate of reaction is independent of the initial concentration of oxidant. However, the close values of $k_2 = \frac{k_1}{[HCOOH]^2}$ show that the order of the reaction with respect to formic acid is two.

Dependence on acid: Effect of acid on the reaction was studied at several initial concentration of perchloric, hydrochloric, sulphuric and acetic

acids. The pseudo first order rate constants increase in the order of the concentration and strength of the acids (Table 2).

Dependence on neutral salts: Neutral salts like chlorides and sulphates were used to study their effect on the oxidation rate. In each case, the salts show a decrease in the first order rate constant.

Dependence on Mn(II): The oxidation rate decreases on addition of manganous sulphate and attains a constant value (Table 3).

Dependence on dielectric constant: It has been observed that rate constant increases inversely with

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TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE ON FORMIC ACID AND PEROXYDICHROMATE CONCENTRATION
Temp. = 45°

[HCOOH] M	[Cr ₂ (Cr ₂ O ₈) ₂] × 10 ³ N	10 ³ k ₁ min ⁻¹	10 ⁴ k ₂ = $\frac{k_1}{[HCOOH]^2}$
3.0	2.50	2.87	3.19
3.5	2.50	4.05	3.31
4.0	2.50	5.42	3.39
4.5	2.50	7.41	3.71
4.8	2.50	8.58	3.72
4.0	1.66	5.47	—
4.0	2.00	5.47	—
4.0	3.33	5.46	—
4.0	5.00	5.41	—

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE ON ACID CONCENTRATION
[HCOOH] = 3.0 M; [Cr₂(Cr₂O₈)₂] = 2.50 × 10⁻³ N; Temp. = 45°

[Acid] × 10 ³ N	10 ³ k ₁ min ⁻¹			
	HClO ₄	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	CH ₃ COOH
1.00	3.45	3.34	3.21	2.98
1.25	3.66	3.50	3.27	3.04
1.66	3.81	3.60	3.37	3.06
2.50	4.72	4.05	3.62	3.09
5.00	5.69	5.34	4.34	3.16

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE ON Mn(II) CONCENTRATION
[HCOOH] = 3.0 M; [Cr₂(Cr₂O₈)₂] = 2.50 × 10⁻³ N; Temp. = 45°

10 ³ k ₁ min ⁻¹	[MnSO ₄] × 10 ⁴ M			
	0.00	2.50	5.00	10.00
	2.87	1.69	1.64	1.63

TABLE 4—DEPENDENCE ON DIELECTRIC CONSTANT
[HCOOH] = 3.0 M; [Cr₂(Cr₂O₈)₂] = 2.50 × 10⁻³ N; Temp. = 45°

10 ³ k ₁ min ⁻¹	[CH ₃ COOH] % v/v				
	10	20	30	40	50
	5.14	8.78	15.75	29.49	63.45

dielectric constant of the medium which was varied by taking binary mixtures of acetic acid-water of different compositions (Table 4). The plot of log k₁ vs 1/D was linear with a positive slope showing the reaction under study to be of ion-dipole type.

Dependence on temperature: The oxidation of formic acid was studied at four different temperatures. Plot of log k₁ vs 1/T showed Arrhenius relationship. Energy parameters are evaluated as E = 15.70 k cal. mole⁻¹, A = 1.021 × 10⁻⁹ sec⁻¹ and ΔS = -86.28 e.u.

Mechanism: In aqueous medium chromium peroxydichromate decomposes as¹⁻⁹:

Peroxy oxygen then reacts readily with the substrate

Table 1 shows that pseudo first order constant is independent of the initial concentration of oxidant which rules out the presence of HCrO₄⁻ as an active species. Step 5 also seems to be not possible as Cr(III) does not have any effect on the oxidation rate (Table 5).

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF Cr(III)

10 ³ k ₁ min ⁻¹	[Cr(III)] × 10 M					
	0.00	1.00	0.50	0.20	0.10	0.05
	2.85	2.84	2.83	2.84	2.83	2.83

Thus, the step 3 seems to be the rate determining step and the rate equation, therefore, involves square power of the formic acid and unit power of Cr(VI) concentrations. The retarding effect of Mn(II) may be explained by assuming that it catalyzes the disproportionation of the intermediate valency of chromium¹⁰⁻¹⁴.

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